

The Implementation of Problem Discovery Evaluation (PDE) to Accelerate Creative Thinking Process in Solving Problems

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Article Info	Abstract
<p>Article History</p> <p>Received: November 21,2025</p> <p>Accepted: February 22,2026</p> <hr/> <p>Keywords : Problem Discovery Evaluation, Creative Thinking, Solving Problems</p> <p>DOI: 10.5281/zenodo.18745644</p>	<p><i>Creative thinking becomes one of the focus in learning mathematics. Creative thinking in learning matemathic is oftenly accosiated with creative problem solving which can be reviewed in creative thinking. Creative thinking process is very important to solve problems not only related to problems in the field. Creative thinking process in solving problems have yet reached what is expected. One of the factors that influence the creative thinking process in solving problems is learning model. The learning model that will be used as a means to make students familiar with the creative thinking process in solving problem is Problem Discovery Evaluation (PDE). The study was conducted to determine the practicability and the effectiveness of Problem Discovery Evaluation in accelerating the process of creative thinking in solving problems. The study was conducted on 24 students of Mathematics Education study program. The instruments of the study are guidelines to observe lecturer's activities, questionnaires of lecturer's responses, guidelines to observe students' activities, questionnaires of students' responses and questions of creative thinking process in solving mathematical problems. The results show that Problem Discovery Education is practical and effective in accelerating the creative thinking process in solving mathematical problems.</i></p>

Introduction

One of the main components in the 21st century education is creativity (Sternberg, 2006; Sternberg, 2012; Navarrete, 2013; Tindowen, Bassig, &Cagurangan, 2017; Kawuryan, Hastuti, &Supartinah, 2018; Suryandari, Fatimah, &Prasetyo, 2018). In the 21st century, schools are also required to have creative thinking, critical thinking and problem solving, communication, and collaboration or commonly referred as the 4Cs (Septikasari and Frasandy, 2018). Therefore, the contemporary curriculum emphasizes on the development of creative thinking skills for students (Vale, & Barbosa, 2015; Sternberg, 2006; Apriliani, &Suyitno, 2016; Sternberg, 2016). Therefore,the creative thinking becomes one of the focuses in mathematics education.

Creative thinking in mathematics is usually associated with problem solving or problem posing (Silver, 1997). Eryvnc (2002) stated that mathematical creative thinking in problem solving is the ability to formulate mathematical objective and to determine the relationship between mathematical concepts. This means that creative thinking is the ability to solve problems based on the suitability of integrating concepts as well as deductive logic in mathematics education to get a solution to a problem.

Pehkonen (1997) stated that creative thinking is a logical and divergent higher order thinking skill to build new ideas that are triggered by various and challenging problems. Logical thinking involves systematic and rational processes in verifying and making valid conclusions (Siswono, 2010). Meanwhile, divergent thinking is seen as a mental operation that requires the use of creative thinking skills, including fluency, flexibility, originality and elaboration in mathematics problem solving and problem posing (Haylock, 1997; Silver, 1997).

According to Isaksen and Treffinger (2004), the creative thinking process contains three main stages, they are: understanding the problem, building ideas, and planning actions. At the stage of understanding the problem, it includes: looking for various possibilities in solving problems, building general problem solving goals, thoroughly examining the problems at hand, determining important data that can be used in problem solving, considering various problem solutions, and constructing or choosing specific problem solutions. Furthermore, the idea-building stage includes: to produces lots of ideas (*fluent*), creating various ideas (*flexible*), be unique (*original*), and identifying in detail (*elaboration*) various alternative possibilities or options that have the potential to solve problems. The last stage includes planning action; at this stage, a person begins to develop criteria to analyze problems, select criteria and apply them to support and strengthen the solutions, consider other possible actions in solving problems, and formulate the solution.

Creative thinking can be viewed from the perspective of Wallas theory as an initial theory in the creative thinking process. Wallas (Kattou, 2015) in his book "*The Art of Thought*" stated that the creative thinking process includes four different stages, they are: 1) *Preparation Stage*, at this stage, students can collect various

relevant informations to the given problem; 2) *Incubation Stage*, at this stage, students break away temporarily from the problems and try to find some inspiration. During the incubation stage, the ideas that arise will be interconnected and arranged in mind without the person directly working on the problem. this stage can last for a few seconds, minutes, or hours depending on the problem to be solved; 3) *Illumination Stage*, at this stage, an idea begins to emerge which is the solution to the given problem; and 4) *Verification Stage*, solutions that have been obtained at the illumination stage need to be identified, checked, refined or developed at the verification stage.

From the description above, it is clear that creative thinking in solving mathematical problems is important so that it must be mastered by elementary school to university students, especially in learning mathematics. The importance of creative thinking in solving mathematical problems is not always in line with the conditions in the field; there are always obstacles in achieving the learning objectives as expressed by Arifin, Kartono and Hidayah (2019) that actually, there are always some obstacles and constraint in learning process. Some studies show that creative thinking in solving the problem is still lacking. Based on the results of research conducted by Maharani, Sukestiyarno, Waluya (2017) it is said that only 16.67% are complete in doing creative thinking in solving problems. Puspitasari, In'am and Syaifuddin (2019) also conducted an analysis of creative thinking in solving problems and the results showed that the highest scored students were in a moderate creative thinking level; that is not creative enough. Problems of creative thinking in solving problems that occur in high school students as showed in the results of research by Maharani, Sukestiyarno, Waluya (2017) and Puspitasari, In'am and Syaifuddin (2019) will certainly have an impact on students. As the results of research by Jaenudin, Kartono, Sukestiyarno, Mariani (2021) that of all students under study, there was not a single student who carried out the creative thinking process in solving problems completely.

Based on the facts described above that the creative thinking process of students in solving mathematical problems is still not as expected. The mathematical creative thinking process is very necessary in learning mathematics, so that they can find the solutions to the existing problems through creative ways. Though, it is not easy to accelerate the process of creative thinking in solving mathematical problems.

Kozlowski, Chamberlin, and Mann (2019) stated that one of the factors that influence mathematical creativity is the learning model and student's creativity. A learning that supports student's creativity has a positive influence on creative thinking (Mann, 2005; Tabach and Friedlander, 2013; Walia, 2012). Cahyati, Muin, and Musyriifah (2018), Huang (2016), Huang (2020) stated that creativity arises because of conditions (atmosphere, environment and community) that support to do some creativity. Of course, conditions like this require a teacher to develop student's creativity (including thinking) in the correct way (Trnova and Josef, 2014).

One of the efforts to familiarize the process of student's creative thinking in solving mathematical problems in this research is by implementing Problem Discovery Evaluation or PDE. PDE is a learning model that is based on the theories of learning by giving the problem, the invention of the solution, and evaluation.

As has been described above, the stages of creative thinking by Wallas consists of the preparation stage, the incubation stage, stage illumination, and verification stage. For the preparation stage and the incubation stage, a learning step is needed that involves giving problems in its implementation. By giving problems frequently in learning, students will be trained in understanding the provided information, changing, and transferring what has been learned. This is in accordance with Bruner's opinion (Dahar, 2006) that in teaching, students are guided through a sequence of statements of a problem or a set of knowledge to improve the ability of students to accept, change, and transfer what they have learned. Teachers should plan lessons in such a way that they can focus on the right problems for students to investigate. It is also in accordance with the social constructivist philosophy that views the mathematical truth is not absolute and identify mathematics as a result of troubleshooting and problem submission by human (Ernest, 1991).

At the stage of illumination and verification, a learning step is needed that emphasizes on the discovery of solutions to the given problems. With learning that emphasizes discovery, students will try on their own to solve problems and express the results of their examinations in the form of conclusions. This is in accordance with the opinion of Bruner (Dahar, 2006) who considers that discovery learning is in accordance with the active search for knowledge by humans and eventually gives the best results. Strive alone to find solutions to the problems and the knowledge that accompanies them, resulting in finding a truly meaningful knowledge. In discovery learning, the real purpose of learning is to acquire knowledge in a way that can exercise their abilities. This is what it means to acquire knowledge through discovery learning. In discovery learning, the teacher should present the required subject matter as a basis for students to solve problems.

The process of creative thinking in solving mathematical problems at each stage requires evaluation. The evaluation in question is not only making conclusions about the findings but evaluating the entire creative thinking process in solving problems. With the evaluation of course, the results of learning can be measured, in accordance with the opinion of Gronlund and Linn (Sugiyanto, Kartowagilan, and Jailani, 2015) that evaluation is a systematic process that aims to collect information, it is interpreted in order to determine the level of success of the target. Hence, the developed PDE model will be a solution to accelerate the creative thinking process in solving mathematical problems.

This article will explain the implementation of PDE model in accelerating the creative thinking process in solving mathematical problems. How is the practicability and effectiveness of PDE in accelerating the creative thinking process in solving mathematical problems and how the effectiveness of the implementation of PDE on the creative thinking process in solving mathematical problems.

Method

Data Source and Research Subject

The data sources of the practicability of PDE come from the activities of the lecturers during the trial PDE learning process, the lecturer's response after carrying out the trial PDE learning, and the PDE learning phenomenon starting from the development of the lesson plan to the process of implementing the trial PDE learning. The data sources of the effectiveness of the model PDE derived from the activities of the students and the classroom atmosphere during the process of testing a PDE learning, work documents of the test process of creative thinking in solving mathematical problems from all of the students in a trial class. The response is most students after carrying out a test of learning models of PDE, and phenomena when following the PDE learning process. The subjects in this study were students of the Mathematics Education study program who contracted the transformation geometry course as many as 24 people.

Data and Instrument Collection Technique

The assessment of lecturer's activities, the technique used to collect the data about lecturer's done by an observer who observes lecturer's activities using the observer activity observation sheet. Lecturer response data were obtained from the results of the questionnaires and interviews with lecturers and observers after completing the lesson. Interviews using open-ended questions in order to know more about the lecturer's response to learning with PDE model, which then will be used to support descriptive analysis of the effectiveness of the creative thinking process. While the lecturer's response questionnaire, the technique used is by giving the lecturer's response questionnaire sheet to the lecturers, practitioners and observers after the implementation of learning.

The students' activities and classroom atmosphere, the technique used to collect data about student activities and classroom atmosphere is done by observing students' activities and classroom atmosphere by using an instrument of students' activity observation sheets and classroom atmosphere. Students' responses were obtained from the results of interviews with several selected students, and the results of questionnaires filled out by all students after finishing the learning. The technique for the interview is to select several very active students, active students and passive students. Interviews used open-ended questions in order to get to know deeply about students' responses to the implementation of learning with the PDE model, which will be used to support descriptive analysis of the effectiveness and the fluency of the creative thinking process in solving mathematical problems. As for the students' response questionnaire, the technique used is to provide a response questionnaire instrument to all students after the implementation of learning.

The completeness of students' learning outcomes for creative thinking process in solving mathematical problems, the technique is done by giving formative tests at the end of the trial learning to all students, individually. The learning test instrument to measure the creative thinking process of students in solving mathematical problems is in the form of questions that have been arranged according to the learning indicators and stages of creative thinking in solving mathematical problems.

Data Analysis

The data of lecturer's activities, lecturer's responses, students' activities and students' responses were recapitulated first and then the average is determined. After obtaining the average value, it was followed by matching the average and the criteria for the following categories.

$4,5 \leq \bar{x} \leq 5$	very good
$3,5 \leq \bar{x} < 4,5$	good
$2,5 \leq \bar{x} < 3,5$	pretty good
$1,5 \leq \bar{x} < 2,5$	lacking
$1 \leq \bar{x} < 1,5$	poor

The PDE model is said to be practical if the theoretical practicability assessment in the form of recommendations from two expert validators and a mathematics education lecturer can be used with minor revisions or can be used without revision, the activities of high lecturers are in the good or very good category or $AD \geq 3,5$, and positive lecturer response that is in the category of fun or very pleasant or $RD \geq 3,5$ including the results of the interview.

The criteria for PDE model to be effectively to accelerate the process of creative thinking in solving mathematical is only if the activity of most students and the classroom atmosphere in the category of high or very high or above 3.5, the response of most students are in the category fun or very unpleasant or $RM \geq 3.5$ including the results of interviews, and the value of the mathematical creative thinking process is above 66 or at least a B category.

In addition, data processing was also carried out statistically on the results of the creative thinking process test in solving problems to determine its effectiveness. On the test results, a completeness test and a proportion test were carried out. Moreover, calculations were made to increase students' creative thinking processes in solving mathematical problems.

Results and Discussion

Learning Impelentation

Learning is done online, using the *Google Classroom* (GC) and *Google Meet* (GM) applications. Modules containing students' activity sheets, test questions, and formative test are distributed through GC. When learning was carried out using GC, the cameras for both students and lecturers are on. The GC and GM used are G-Suit for education so that the use of GM can be done in large quantities. Implementation of Learning with GM can be seen in Figure 1.

Figure 1. The Implementation of Learning Using GM

Observers join the GM to observe the activities of lecturers and students' on an online learning with the PDE model.

The PDE learning was piloted online using *Google Meet* and *Google Classroom*. The effectiveness of online learning depends on the creativity of the teacher. Furthermore, Irvan, Kusumaningrum, Yulia and Widodo (2020) said that online learning has limitations in learning mathematics, including writing mathematical symbols. Therefore, in overcoming these limitations, the modules are used as a learning media. The consideration in using *Google Classroom* is that it can help teachers in organizing classes and monitoring students to learn and of course *Google Classroom* is easy to use, time saving, flexible, free and easily accessible (Iftakhar, 2016). Complementing the use of GC in learning, especially in the delivery of motivation and scaffolding, the researchers also used GM. Several studies have shown that the use of *Google Meet* in online lectures can have a positive impact on students (Al-Marroof, et al., 2020; Ningsih 2020).

Practicability and Validity of PDE model

The practicability of implementing the PDE model was determined from the activities, responses and interviews of lecturers. Practical data from 3 trials where each experiment was carried out for 4 meetings can be seen in Table 1 below.

Table 1. Results of the Practical Assessment of the Implementation of the PDE Learning

Experiment	Lecturer's activity (Practical if > 3,4)	Lecturer's response (Practical if > 3,4)	Summary
Experiment 1	3.61	4.31	Practical
Experiment 2	4.21	4.35	Practical
Experiment 3	4.70	4.75	Practical

Average	4.17	4.47	Practical
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The average assessment of lecturer's activity observations in the implementation of PDE model is 4.17, and the average assessment of lecturer's response questionnaires is 4.47. The results of the interviews with lecturers show that the PDE model is very good because it can activate students; students become more creative and critic in dealing with the given problems. Lecturers feel the need and convinced to apply the PDE model to other materials.

The data on the effectiveness of the implementation of the PDE model were determined from students' activities, students' responses, assessment of creative thinking process in solving mathematical problems, and students' interviews. The summary of effectiveness data from 3 trials can be seen in Table 2 below.

Table 2. the Assessment Results of the Effectiveness of the PDE Learning Implementation

	Students' activity (Effective if > 3,4)	Students' response (Effective if > 3,4)	Creative Thinking Skill in Solving Mathematical Problems (Effective if > 65)	Summary
Experiment 1	3,93	4,35	79,5	Effective
Experiment 2	4,25	4,59	82,38	Effective
Experiment 3	4,80	4,66	83,54	Effective
Average	4,33	4,53	81,80	Effective

The average value of student's activity is 4.33 in the range of $4.2 < VaAS \leq 5$ which is in very good category, for the average value of student response is 4.53 in the range of $4.2 < VaRS \leq 5$ which is in a very pleasant category, and the average creative thinking process in solving mathematical problems is 81.80 in the range of $70 \leq RHB < 90$ which is in high learning achievement category. The results of students' interviews related to the learning steps of PDE model, students felt happy because they were challenged to find solutions to the given problems. In addition, students were also invited to find conceptual association based on problems from routine problems that were given. Students feel the need to apply the PDE model to other materials because it can accelerate critical and creative attitudes, be independent, and know that many problems in everyday life can be solved with mathematical concepts.

Hypothesis Test

The Implementation of the PDE model is effective if more than 75% of students get creative thinking process test scores above 65 in solving mathematical problems (reaching the applied minimum completeness criteria) and more than 75% of students experience an increasing in their creative thinking process in solving mathematical problems at least in the medium category.

The completeness test is used to determine the student's individual and classical mastery achievement in the transformation geometry course. The individual mastery test is used to find out whether the students' average creative thinking process in solving mathematical problems has reached more than 65 or not. The class average completeness test used a one-sided test. The hypothesis proposed is as follows.

H_0 : $\mu \leq 65$ (the average creative thinking process in solving mathematical problems of students who receive learning using PDE model ≤ 65)

H_a : $\mu > 65$ (the average creative thinking process in solving mathematical problems of students who receive learning using the PDE model > 65).

Decision criteria, reject H_0 if $t_{table} \geq t_{critic}$ with $dk = (n-1)$ and significance level at 5%. The results of the analysis can be seen in table 3.

Table 3.the Analysis of Completeness Test

Test Value = 65			
t	df	Sig. (2-tailed)	95% Confidence Interval of the Mean Difference

					Lower	Upper
TKBKM	5.429	23	.000	13.917	8.61	19.22

From the calculation result, it is obtained that sig. (2-tailed) is at 0.001, then for 1-tailed obtained is at 0.002 as well. Where sig. $0.002 < 0.05$, then H_0 is rejected. This means that the average creative thinking process in solving mathematical problems of students who received learning using the PDE model is > 65 .

The formulation of the hypothesis to test the proportion of completeness with asignificance level of 5% is formulated as follows.

- H_0 : $\pi \leq 75$ (the proportion of students in learning with the PDE model who achieves the minimum completeness criteria has not exceeded or equal to 75%)
 H_a : $\pi > 75$ (the proportion of students in learning using the PDE model who achieves the minimum completeness criteria has exceeded 75%).

Table 4. Completeness Proportion Test

	Category	N	Observed Prop.	Test Prop.	Exact Sig. (1-tailed)
Completeness	Group 1	No	2	.08	.000 ^a
	Group 2	Complete	22	.92	
	Total		24	1.00	

a. Alternative hypothesis states that the proportion of cases in the first group $< .75$.

Based on the results of the analysis, it is obtained that the exact sig. (1-tailed) is $0.000 < 0.05$ (5%), then H_0 is rejected. This means that the proportion of students in learning using the PDE model who achieves the minimum completeness criteria has exceeded 75%.

Table 5. Improving the creative thinking process in solving mathematical problems

Category	Total
High	8
Medium	16
Low	0

In Table 5, it can be seen that there are 16 students with moderate improvement (66.6%) and 8 students (33.3%). The test results show that the PDE model is practical and effective in accelerating students' creative thinking processes in solving mathematical problems. This happens because the PDE model used is based on the problem-solving, discovery and evaluation learning model. Where the PDE model consists of 5 stages: the problem orientation stage, the observation stage, the discovery stage, the confirmation stage, and the evaluation stage. In each phase of the PDE model, it supports the acceleration process of creative thinking in solving mathematical problems.

The problem orientation stage in the PDE model is a learning activity to condition students to be ready to learn. The main activity in this stage is to present the suitable problems and in accordance with the material to be studied. Giving problems in accordance with the concept to be studied aims to condition students on the material to be studied. Through this problem, students are expected to be able to construct their knowledge based on the concepts they already have. This is in accordance with the opinion of Gunantara, Suarjana, and Riastini (2014) who stated that problems are used to relate students' curiosity, analytical skills, and initiative to the subject matter. Giving this kind of problems also indirectly motivates students to have the knowledge and ability to solve them. Walter and Halt (Irvine, 2015) stated that the sources of motivation include interesting tasks, learning environments, opportunities to find out, and the reason to use these objects and help others.

The observation stage in the PDE model encourages students to identify and organize the provided information on problems and be able to plan the solutions to these problems. The activity of understanding the problem is carried out by identifying and organizing the information contained in the problem, such as recording the information. In planning problem solving solutions, researchers presented questions that guide them in working on existing problems. Giving these questions aims as scaffolding, so that students can find their own concepts. Scaffolding should be given individually considering the difficulty or ability of each student is not the same. This is in line with the theory as stated by Slavin

(2010) that the preparation of learning and the use of scaffolding will differ depending on the level of student's knowledge.

The discovery stage in PDE model is a learning activity that strengthens the creative thinking process in solving students' mathematical problems through the discovery process. The discovery stage is developed based on the discovery learning model. Discovery learning explains about students getting to know a problem, the characteristics of the solution and carrying out the chosen strategy (Borthick and Jones, 2000). Therefore, at this stage students will pour and mould it in written form the plans that have been arranged at the observation stage. In the previous stage, students have succeeded in finding the concepts to be used, in this stage, scaffolding is used to find the association between concepts in solving problems. Students are led by questions that make students reason to find solutions to problems. Lecturers give freedom to students in expressing their findings. This is certainly one of the efforts to provide opportunities for students to be creative, as Wahyudi, Waluya, Rochmad(2018) stated that creativity exists because of opportunity. Where the ability to think creatively will grow because of the students' creativity (Wahyudi, Waluya, Rochmad and Suyitno, 2018).

The confirmation stage in PDE model is a learning activity to re-check what has been done whether it is in accordance with the concepts and creative thinking process in solving mathematical problems. Activities in this stage are often missed by students. In general, after finding a solution there is no more checking process. So this confirmation process must be familiarized through learning activities. Sripatmi and Ningsih (2020) said that in confirmation activities, students will get feedbacks on the validity, feasibility or acceptability of knowledge, skills or attitudes. So that with this confirmation activity there will be no conceptual errors experienced by students when students construct their knowledge to the fullest (Gita and Apsari, 2018).

The evaluation stage in PDE model is a learning activity to conduct self-evaluation related to the concepts that have been taught and the creative thinking process in solving mathematical problems that have been studied, as well as the follow-up learning. The definition of evaluation according to Gronlund and Linn (Sugiyanto, Kartowagilan, and Jailani, 2015) is a systematic process that aims to collect information, it is interpreted in order to determine the level of success of the target. The evaluation process needs to be carried out to be able to measure the success of the planned learning implementation. This is in accordance with the opinion of Gülten (2013) and Saad, et al. (2010) that the implementation of learning is the implementation of learning plan and its success must be measured or evaluated.

Conclusion

The data on the practicability of the learning model were obtained from observations of lecturer's activities, lecturer's responses and lecturer's interviews. The test results show that the PDE model is practical in accelerating the creative thinking process in solving mathematical problems. At the trial stage, in addition to obtaining practical data, effective data were also obtained. Data on the effectiveness of PDE model were obtained from students' activities data, students' responses and interviews. Based on the three data, the results show that PDE model is effective in accelerating the creative thinking process in solving mathematical problems. Learning with the PDE model to accelerate the creative thinking process in solving mathematical problems consists of five stages; they are the problem orientation stage, the observation stage, the discovery stage, the confirmation stage, and the evaluation stage.

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